

The Influence Of Content Marketing And Viral Marketing On Purchase Decisions At Norma Coffee On The Millennial Generation In Pekanbaru

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ABSTRACT

Norma Coffee is a coffee shop in Pekanbaru that focuses on creating a comfortable atmosphere for various activities, offering high-quality products, and prioritizing consistent, warm, and friendly service. The purpose of this study is to determine the influence of Content Marketing and Viral Marketing on TikTok on Purchase Decisions at Norma Coffee among the Millennial Generation in Pekanbaru. The sample size in this study is 96 respondents, selected using purposive sampling. Data collection was conducted by distributing questionnaires to the respondents. Both primary and secondary data were used. The data analysis method applied is multiple linear regression using SPSS 29 software. The results of partial testing show that the Content Marketing and Viral Marketing variables each have a partial influence on Purchase Decisions. Simultaneous testing results indicate that Content Marketing and Viral Marketing on TikTok have a positive and significant impact on Purchase Decisions at Norma Coffee among the Millennial Generation in Pekanbaru. The R Square value of 0.491, or 49.1%, indicates that Content Marketing and Viral Marketing collectively account for 49.1% of the influence on the Purchase Decision variable, while the remaining 50.9% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study.

INTRODUCTION

According to Shilfiyo and Rummyeni (2022), content marketing is a strategic marketing approach focused on creating and distributing relevant, valuable, and consistent content to attract and retain a clearly defined target audience, thereby encouraging customers to take beneficial actions. Companies can distribute content marketing through various media, including social media. One social media platform experiencing rapid growth and widely used by the public is TikTok.

TikTok is a platform that allows users to create, watch, and share short videos of a specific duration. The app is equipped with various video editing features, such as animations, text and sticker additions, and advanced special effects, enabling users to add background music and create creative content (Massie, 2020). TikTok ranked among the top 3 most popular apps in Indonesia in 2023, according to DataReportal.

Source : DataReportal, 2023.

Figure 1. 1 : Graph of Most Used Social Media Platforms in Indonesia, 2023.

Based on Figure 1.1, TikTok ranks third, having surpassed Instagram in popularity. According to DataReportal, TikTok is the top platform for generating organic traffic, attributed to its high engagement rate and growth rate among users compared to other social media platforms. As TikTok is one of the fastest-growing social media platforms, businesses like Norma Coffee are increasingly interested in using TikTok for content marketing to promote their products. Below is an overview of the Norma Coffee TikTok social media account :

Source : Norma Coffee's TikTok Social Media Account.

Figure 1. 2 : Profile of Norma Coffee's TikTok Account.

As a coffee shop leveraging social media technology, Norma Coffee uses its TikTok account, @normacoffee, to showcase unique elements in each posted content. Based on Figure 1.2, the TikTok account, created in 2022, has gained 522 followers and has posted around 184 videos to date. The consistent publication of engaging content on Norma Coffee's TikTok account since 2022 has prompted the author to study content marketing and its influence on purchasing decisions.

Users often use TikTok to market trending products or capitalize on popular topics, known as viral marketing. Each piece of content on TikTok is analyzed by the system, which automatically displays content on the For You Page (FYP) of all TikTok users. Content with high engagement rates may be featured on the FYP, an essential component of viral marketing strategy for any business. A product video's success in reaching others' FYP enables it to spread across various social media platforms, allowing a broader audience to engage with it. Consequently, businesses can achieve their marketing objectives more effectively (Riani & Nuriyanti, 2020). Below is an overview of FYP videos related to Norma Coffee :

Source : TikTok Social Media.

Figure 1. 3 : FYP Content About Norma Coffee.

Based on Figure 1.3, many of the posts published by Norma Coffee have reached the For You Page (FYP), which contributes to the viral effect. Not only Norma Coffee, but other users on TikTok who also publish content related to Norma Coffee have also seen their posts on the FYP. When used effectively, the content published on TikTok can enhance the target market's interest in making purchase decisions.

According to an interview conducted by the researcher with a visitor to Norma Coffee, Mrs. Asna, she explained that she learned about Norma Coffee from content that appeared on the FYP on TikTok. The content showcased the comfortable atmosphere of Norma Coffee, which is ideal for relaxing with family and friends. Similarly, Mrs. Naomi Natali mentioned that she had heard about Norma Coffee before but was not initially interested in visiting until she saw content related to Norma Coffee from the @kulinerpku account on her TikTok FYP. The content highlighted the cozy ambiance of Norma Coffee and its varied menu, which piqued her interest in visiting.

The main difference between content marketing and viral marketing is that content marketing pertains to the creation of content on social media platforms, while viral marketing focuses more on widely popular and heavily discussed content (Rimbahari et al., 2023). Both aspects are important to study, as they have the potential to influence the purchasing decisions of consumers and potential customers.

Purchasing decisions involve the steps consumers take to identify problems, gather information about products or brands, and evaluate each option to resolve those issues, ultimately leading to the decision to buy (Tjiptono, 2020). Below are the sales data for Norma Coffee for the period 2021-2023 :

Table 1. 1 : Sales Data of Norma Coffee for the Years 2021-2023

No	Year	Category	Sales (Product)
1	2021	Drink	79.319
		Food	33.515
		Pastry	13.520
Total			126.354

2	2022	Drink	66.993
		Food	41.176
		Pastry	16.156
Total			124.325
3	2023	Drink	63.482
		Food	55.474
		Pastry	14.081
Total			133.037

Source : Sales Data Of Norma Coffee.

According to Table 1.1, product sales decreased by 1.6% in 2022 but increased by 7% in 2023. The increase in 2023 is considered significant. The author intends to investigate whether this increase in sales is a result of content marketing and viral marketing on the TikTok platform, as the Norma Coffee TikTok account was created in 2022. This aligns with the research conducted by T. B. Putri et al. (2023), which found that content marketing has a positive influence on purchasing decisions. It also corresponds with the research by Aziza et al. (2022), which indicates that viral marketing significantly affects purchasing decisions.

Based on the background provided, the author is interested in conducting a study titled **“THE INFLUENCE OF CONTENT MARKETING AND VIRAL MARKETING ON PURCHASE DECISIONS AT NORMA COFFEE ON THE MILLENNIAL GENERATION IN PEKANBARU.”**

LITERATURE RESEARCH

2.1 Marketing Management

Marketing management is defined as the art and science of identifying target markets and undertaking efforts to enhance customer value in order to attract, retain, and develop customer value. Marketing management occurs when at least one party initiates a potential trade and determines how to elicit the desired response from the other party (Kotler & Keller, 2016).

2.2 Purchase Decisions

Purchase decision is a phase in the buying process where consumers actively conduct the transaction of purchasing a product or service after going through a series of prior stages (Kotler & Armstrong, 2014). According to Tjiptono (2020), a purchase decision is the step in which consumers recognize specific products or brands and evaluate how well each option meets their needs, ultimately influencing their purchasing decisions.

2.3 Content Marketing

Content marketing involves the process of creating and distributing relevant and valuable content, with the aim of attracting, engaging, and involving a specific audience in an easily understandable way. The goal is to encourage customers to take beneficial actions (Milhinhos, 2015). Content marketing is a strategy used to define a brand's identity, intending to change passive consumer behavior through engaging and non-intrusive brand dialogues, especially on appropriate media platforms (Du Plessis, 2015).

2.4 Viral Marketing

According to Kotler & Armstrong (2018), viral marketing is a digital adaptation of electronic word-of-mouth marketing that involves the production of highly shareable videos, advertisements, and other marketing content, prompting consumers to actively seek out or share this content with their friends. Viral marketing is a marketing effort that encourages consumers to share their positive experiences about a product with others (Rinandiyana et al., 2022). This benefits companies by reducing marketing expenses and increasing time productivity.

Theoretical Framework

Figure 2. 1 : Theoretical Framework

Description :

METHOD

The research object is Norma Coffee. This study was conducted at Norma Coffee, located at Jl. Muchtar Lutfi No.69, Simpang Baru, Kec. Tampan, Pekanbaru City, Riau 28292. Quantitative data is used in this research, consisting of numerical values or numerical data that are then processed. The data sources used are primary and secondary data. In the context of this research, the sampling technique employed is non-probability sampling, requiring a sample size of 96 individuals. The data collection technique used is a questionnaire. The data analysis techniques employed are measurement scale and quantitative analysis. The quality testing of the data includes validity and reliability tests. The classical assumption tests applied are normality test, multicollinearity test, and heteroscedasticity test. The hypothesis tests conducted include partial tests (t-test), simultaneous tests (F-test), and the coefficient of determination.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Data Quality Assessment

1. Validity Test

Table 5. 1 : Validity Test Result

No.	Variable	Statement	R (calculate)	R (table)	Description
1	Content Marketing	X1.1	0,791	0,200	VALID
		X1.2	0,849	0,200	VALID
		X1.3	0,853	0,200	VALID
		X1.4	0,821	0,200	VALID
		X1.5	0,774	0,200	VALID
2	Viral Marketing	X2.1	0,803	0,200	VALID
		X2.2	0,845	0,200	VALID

3	Purchase Decision	X2.3	0,846	0,200	VALID
		X2.4	0,844	0,200	VALID
		Y1	0,722	0,200	VALID
		Y2	0,788	0,200	VALID
		Y3	0,774	0,200	VALID
		Y4	0,861	0,200	VALID
		Y5	0,821	0,200	VALID

Source : SPSS Data Processing Results, 2024.

Based on the table above, it can be seen that all $r_{calculate} > r_{table}$ 0,200 indicating that all statement items used are valid in this study and can be used to measure the target variable.

2. Reliability Test

Table 5. 2 : Results Of The Reliability Test For The Content Marketing Variable

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.876	5

Source : SPSS Data Processing Results, 2024.

Table 5.6 shows that the questionnaire used in this study is considered reliable. This is supported by the reliability test result, with a Cronbach's Alpha of 0,876 > 0,60, based on a total of 5 statements.

Table 5. 3 : Results Of The Reliability Test For The Viral Marketing Variable

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.854	4

Source : SPSS Data Processing Results, 2024.

Table 5.7 shows that the questionnaire used in this study is deemed reliable. This is demonstrated by the reliability test result, with a Cronbach's Alpha of 0,854 > 0,60, based on a total of 4 statements.

Table 5. 4 : Results Of The Reliability Test For The Purchase Decision Variable

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.853	5

Source : SPSS Data Processing Results, 2024.

Table 5.8 shows that the questionnaire used in this study is considered reliable. This is evidenced by the reliability test result, with a Cronbach's Alpha of 0,853 > 0,60, based on a total of 5 statements.

B. Classical Assumption Test

1. Normality Test

Table 5. 5 : Normality Test Results

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		
		Unstandardized Residual
N		96
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	2.79645517
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.078
	Positive	.070
	Negative	-.078
Test Statistic		.078

Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) ^c	.185
Monte Carlo Sig. (2-tailed) ^d Sig.	.160
99% Confidence Interval Lower Bound	.151
Upper Bound	.170
a. Test distribution is Normal.	
b. Calculated from data.	
c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.	
d. Lilliefors' method based on 10000 Monte Carlo samples with starting seed 2000000.	

Source : SPSS Data Processing Results, 2024.

From Table 5.9, it can be observed that the significance value of the normality test exceeds 0.05, specifically 0.185 > 0.05. Therefore, it can be concluded that the data distribution is normal.

2. Multicollinearity Test

Table 5. 6 : Multicollinearity Test Results

Model	Coefficients ^a					Collinearity Statistics	
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
1 (Constant)	5.087	1.680		3.028	.003		
Content Marketing	.358	.089	.371	4.030	<,001	.644	1.552
Viral Marketing	.497	.111	.413	4.478	<,001	.644	1.552

a. Dependent Variable: Keputusan Pembelian

Source : SPSS Data Processing Results, 2024.

The results of the multicollinearity test indicate that the VIF value for the content marketing variable (X1) is 1.552, which is less than 10, with a tolerance value of 0.543, which is greater than 0.10. Similarly, the viral marketing variable (X2) has a VIF value of 1.552 and a tolerance of 0.644. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity among the independent variables, as all VIF values are below 10 and the tolerance values exceed 0.10. Thus, the second condition of the classical assumption test is satisfied.

3. Heteroscedastisity Test

Table 5. 7 : Heteroscedastisity Test Results

Model	Coefficients ^a					Collinearity Statistics	
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
1 (Constant)	3.969	1.095		3.626	<,001		
Content Marketing	-.067	.058	-.146	-	.253	.644	1.552
Viral Marketing	-.031	.072	-.054	-.427	.670	.644	1.552

a. Dependent Variable: Abs_RES

Source : SPSS Data Processing Results, 2024.

Based on Table 5.11, it can be observed that there is no heteroscedasticity in the data for this test. This is evidenced by the significance (sig) value being greater than 0.05, indicating that there are no signs of heteroscedasticity in the regression model.

C. Multiple Linear Regression Test

Table 5. 8 : Multiple Linear Regression Test Result

Model	Coefficients ^a						Collinearity Statistics	
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	T	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF	
	B	Std. Error						
1 (Constant)	5.087	1.680		3.028	.003			
Content Marketing	.358	.089	.371	4.030	<,001	.644	1.552	
Viral Marketing	.497	.111	.413	4.478	<,001	.644	1.552	

a. Dependent Variable: Keputusan Pembelian

Source : SPSS Data Processing Results, 2024.

The calculation results yield a constant value of 5.087. The regression coefficients are X1 = 0.358 and X2 = 0.497. Based on these calculations, the regression equation is $Y = 5.087 + 0.358X1 + 0.497X2$.

From the multiple regression equation above, it can be stated that:

- a) The constant value of 5.087 means that the value of the dependent variable will equal this constant even when the independent variables are zero.
- b) The coefficient for X1 (content marketing) is 0.358, indicating that a 1% increase in the content marketing variable will increase the purchase decision by 0.358 units, assuming all other variables remain constant.
- c) The coefficient for X2 (viral marketing) is 0.497, indicating that a 1% increase in the viral marketing variable will increase the purchase decision by 0.497 units, assuming all other variables remain constant.

D. Hypothesis Test

1. Partial Test (T Test)

Table 5. 9 : T Test Result

Model	Coefficients ^a						Collinearity Statistics	
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	T	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF	
	B	Std. Error						
1 (Constant)	5.087	1.680		3.028	.003			
Content Marketing	.358	.089	.371	4.030	<,001	.644	1.552	
Viral Marketing	.497	.111	.413	4.478	<,001	.644	1.552	

a. Dependent Variable: Keputusan Pembelian

Source : SPSS Data Processing Results, 2024.

Based on Table 5.13, hypothesis testing can be conducted as follows :

- 1. Hypothesis Testing for H1
The significance value for the effect of X1 on Y is ($<0.001 < 0.05$), and the calculated t-value is $4.030 > 1.985$. Therefore, it can be concluded that H1 is accepted, indicating that X1 has an effect on Y.
- 2. Hypothesis Testing for H2
The significance value for the effect of X2 on Y is ($<0.001 < 0.05$), and the calculated t-value is $4.478 > 1.985$. Therefore, it can be concluded that H2 is accepted, indicating that X2 has an effect on Y.

2. Simultaneous Test (F Test)

Tabel 5. 10 : F Test Result

ANOVA ^a					
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	716.574	2	358.287	44.851	<,001 ^b
Residual	742.915	93	7.988		
Total	1459.490	95			

a. Dependent Variable: Keputusan Pembelian
b. Predictors: (Constant), Viral Marketing, Content Marketing

Source : SPSS Data Processing Results, 2024.

From Table 5.14, it is known that the simultaneous effect of independent variables on the dependent variable is tested by comparing the F-table with the calculated F-value. The hypothesis is accepted if the calculated F-value > F-table and the significance value < 0.05. The significance level (α) used is 0.05. With degrees of freedom (df) $n - k = 93$, the F-table result is 3.09. The calculated F-value is 44.851, with a significance value of <0.001.

Thus, the calculated F-value > F-table, that is, $44.851 > 3.09$, with sig (<0.001) < 0.05. This indicates that the regression model can be used to test the simultaneous influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable, meaning that content marketing and viral marketing simultaneously influence purchasing decisions.

3. Coefficient of Determination

Table 5. 11 : Result of the Coefficient of Determination Test

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.701 ^a	.491	.480	2.826

a. Predictors: (Constant), Viral Marketing, Content Marketing

Source : SPSS Data Processing Results, 2024.

It is known that the R-squared value is 0.491, which means that content marketing and viral marketing contribute significantly to influencing purchasing decisions by 49.1%, while the remaining percentage is determined by other variables that affect purchasing decisions.

E. Research Results

1. The Influence of Content marketing on Purchase Decisions

The company needs to implement strategies to achieve the goal of generating profits. Content marketing is used as a competitive strategy that can be positioned as a competitive advantage for the company. The strength of content marketing as a strategic approach in marketing lies in its focus on creating and distributing valuable, relevant, and consistent content, enabling content marketing to create a new concept in the marketing world.

According to research conducted by Diawati *et al.* (2021), content marketing on the TikTok platform has a significant impact on purchasing decisions. Content marketing has become essential in business for generating value from consumers to compete in today's digital era. The content shared on TikTok has benefited consumers by providing them with information about available products and promotions, while still being engaging enough to influence consumers to make purchases.

The research results regarding the influence of content marketing on purchasing decisions at Norma Coffee indicate that the calculated t_{value} is greater than the calculated t_{table} , specifically $4.030 > 1.986$, and the significance value of the t-test is less than 0.05, that is, (<0.001) < 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_0)

is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis (H_a) is accepted, indicating that content marketing has a significant effect on purchasing decisions. These findings are consistent with previous research conducted by Dewi et al. (2023), titled "The Influence of Content Marketing and Electronic Word of Mouth on the TikTok Platform on Purchasing Decisions in Shopee," which found that content marketing significantly affects purchasing decisions in Shopee.

The results of the SPSS analysis in this study support the theory proposed by Milhinhos (2015), which states that content marketing involves the process of creating and distributing relevant and valuable content, with the aim of attracting, inviting, and engaging a specific and easily understood audience. The goal is to encourage customers to take beneficial actions.

2. The Influence of Viral Marketing on Purchasing Decisions

The social media platform TikTok features a page preview option where anyone who is friends with or follows the sender can see what is shared by both well-known figures and lesser-known individuals. Consequently, every post from users will be visible to all their friends. Indirectly, the more interactions that occur, the more viral the news or products posted on social media become. The virality of a product will impact its price and value.

According to research conducted by Putri *et al.* (2022), viral marketing has a significant impact on consumer choices. This highlights that the performance of viral marketing has been effective in assisting customers in making purchasing decisions, and it has been proven that viral marketing significantly influences purchasing decisions. Products are highly sought after due to the nature of viral marketing, which operates like a virus. Viral marketing can affect customers' decisions to buy a product if that product has been successfully made viral and spreads, generating curiosity and leading customers to decide to purchase.

The results of the research on the influence of viral marketing on purchasing decisions at Norma Coffee indicate that the calculated t_{value} is greater than the calculated t_{table} , specifically $4.478 > 1.985$, and the significance value of the t-test is less than 0.05, that is, $(<0.001) < 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis (H_a) is accepted, indicating that viral marketing has a significant effect on purchasing decisions.

The results of the SPSS analysis in this study support the theory proposed by Kotler & Armstrong (2018), which states that viral marketing methods possess highly contagious characteristics, prompting consumers or customers to voluntarily spread and share them with their friends.

CONCLUSION

1. Content Marketing has a significant effect on Purchasing Decisions at Norma Coffee. This is evidenced by the t-test significance value of 4.030, with a significance level of $(0.001) < 0.05$. The researcher concludes that in this study, respondents are interested in purchasing a product if the company has good and engaging content marketing. Content marketing plays a crucial role in maintaining the loyalty of the target audience, as high-quality content can entice customers to return and persuade them to choose Norma Coffee's products over its competitors.
2. Viral Marketing has a significant effect on Purchasing Decisions at Norma Coffee. This is evidenced by the t-test significance value of 4.478, with a significance level of $(0.001) < 0.05$. The researcher concludes that respondents choose to make purchases at Norma Coffee due to recommendations from others, whether from those around them or influencers on social media. Additionally, the content presented on Norma Coffee's TikTok account is engaging enough to capture the audience's attention and generate extensive discussion.
3. Content Marketing and Viral Marketing, when combined, have a significant effect on Purchasing Decisions at Norma Coffee. This is evidenced by the F-test significance value of 44.851, with a significance level of $(0.001) < 0.05$.

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